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BIONOVFOOD

BionovFOOD, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)
Postdoctoral Project

INNOVATIVE GREEN SOLUTIONS FOR DISTILLERY BY- PRODUCTS VALORIZATION AND PROTEIN-RICH INGREDIENT PRODUCTION

About BionovFOOD

The BionovFOOD project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101105437, valorizes winery and distillery by-products through fungal biorefineries, delivering sustainable protein ingredients and fungi-based meat analogues for a circular food system.

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Published research and conferences

- Sustainable Repurposing of Grape Marc: Potential for Bio-Based Innovations (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2025.114871>).
- Grape Marc. Biotransformation to Protein-Rich Food Ingredients using Fungal Fermentation (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.focha.2025.101058>).
- Biotransforming EU Wine and Distillery By-products: Grape Marc Valorization via Edible Filamentous Fungi for Sustainable Protein Production (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16858666>)
- A new biorefinery approach utilizing edible Ascomycetes and Zygomycetes filamentous fungi to valorize vinasse generated by the distillery industry (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16858029>).
- Winery by-products as potential bioresources for green valorization and sustainable biotechnological applications (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16878435>)
- Innovative Approaches for Bioconverting Wine Lees into Protein-Rich Fungal Biomass – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16849366>
- Innovative solutions for wine and distillery by-products valorization into climate-smart protein sources using filamentous fungi (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16878332>)
- Harnessing Winery and Distillery By-Products with *Aspergillus oryzae*: Potential for development of innovative fungi-based fermented food and feed (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16878450>)
- Mycoprotein from Winery by-products: Assessing In vitro protein digestibility and mineral Bioaccessibility (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16855054>).

More groundbreaking research updates coming soon...